

COMPARATIVE STUDY OF EDUCATION OF CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY IN THE HIGHER INSTITUTION (SOCIAL WORK AND BUSINESS SCHOOLS/DEPARTMENTS) OF INDIA

Nitesh Pathak

Research Scholar, Department of Social Work, University of Lucknow, Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh, India

Paper Received On: 21 JUNE 2023

Peer Reviewed On: 30 JUNE 2023

Published On: 01 JULY 2023

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Introduction: Mahatma Gandhi wants the owner of businesses should behave like trust. They earn for the society and the owner should be only patron of the trust on behalf of the society. This was the trusteeship principle based on ancient Indian understanding of wealth and social well-being. When it comes about the behaviour of corporate and businesses towards society. This is well understood in Indian context that they should contribute to make it better. This understanding is very old and one can easily find these things in folk traditions and other literary works. Although this responsibility was voluntary for the businesses but most desirable by the society. Corporate social responsibility is an extension of this tradition in India.

In Modern context, Corporate social responsibility is by-product of the understanding that corporate should be responsible for society and environment surrounding, we reached in this understanding after a long debate about this. Corporate social responsibility has been the subject of much investigation and the debate for many years among both researchers and practitioners (*Ibrahim et al. 2006*). This Understanding has break the notion that corporate should have only responsibility of making more and more profit. The participants of this debate were both from corporate and non-corporate fields such as academics, social worker, environment activist etc. As we come on understanding that this should be done, Business started working on how this will

become profitable for them. They adopted many innovative business ideas such as Unilever's Shakti, which help them to fulfil both their motive for business as well as their responsibility towards society.

As business adopted it many business schools started courses on it to help their graduates to understand about it and become prepare to deal with it. Despite the efforts and the continued preoccupation on the role of business in society few studies to date, has tried jointly CSR analysis conducted by the company and the value structure of the society to which the CSR addressed. This shortage is even greater in the context of higher education (Weber et al. 2004)

Corporate social responsibility is basically the initiative of corporate for the betterment of the society and environment. In this process they do some activity which help in improving social functioning of the individuals and society. This is an important work and requires professions and experts of these fields. This is the core work of the social worker. Many corporate social responsibility related initiatives requires trend professionals of social work. But there are no significant research or literature is available which talks about how the professionals of social work is getting ready for these type of work. This paper is one of the initiatives which is trying to understand comparatively the syllabus and content of courses related to corporate social responsibility in business and social work schools. This will also analyse what type of courses are running in these institutions and how much attention is getting by courses related to CSR in these institutions.

So the objective of the paper is as follow:

- (1) To find about courses on CSR in Schools and departments of Social works and in business schools in India.
- (2) To analyze the syllabus and its contents of courses.
- (3) To analyze the Focus of institute on Courses related to CSR.
- (4) To draw some insights on CSR education in Higher education institutes of India.
- (5) To find suggestions for the schools/department of social work in helping their student to become better professional of CSR.

Methodology: The paper is based on secondary data. The data is collected through the information available on the website of selected schools. The researcher tried to verify these data through head of department by mail.

The schools and departments were selected through random sampling method. The criteria for becoming eligible department/school for this study was the department/school must have MSW/MA in social work programme with more than one specializations. After qualifying criteria check a list of institutions were made. Then a chit was made for each School/department and then randomly through these chits the institutions were selected.

Following steps adopted for analysing the Course and syllabus

- After selecting the schools/Institutes, the programme and syllabus (Latest) was searched at website of the Institution.
- In different programmes it was looked that if there is any course of corporate social responsibility.
- After that the content of syllabus was checked for Corporate Social Responsibility related units.

Genesis and concepts: Every civilization has its own understanding of role of businesses for the society. These roles are very much voluntary choices. During the industrial revolution profit was only and ultimate motive of businesses. As the time passes it was realized that there is need of responsible behavior by the businesses towards society and environment. The argument behind CSR is as businesses are using resources of society from environment and making profit from that and causing harm to them. So this should be obligation of the business to take care of those society and environment, This causes some business groups e.g. Ford, Rockefeller to start their social initiatives. In the fifties of 20th century this debate got moment after carols pyramids of responsibility. A good amount of researches was done. Now this become a major point of discussion that corporate should act for societal and environmental issues. Although there are still people who are in favor that corporate and its manager only focus on profit making. The work by many scholars leads to many businesses to start Social responsibility related endeavor. Now this debate is approximately settled in favor of Corporate Social Responsibility.

Initially corporate do social welfare work for making their image better. This was voluntary in this sense. But as time passes people understand that the expense of making profit by the corporate is bear by whole society and environment. so now Corporate Social Responsibility is based on principle of triple bottom line which is planet, profit and people. This suggest that corporate should make their profit in such a way which

causes sustainability of planet, the earth and its resources, and betterment of life of people of the planet. This includes taking care of their employees, customers along with surrounding society and environment. One of the current debate in CSR is now that whether CSR should be voluntary or mandatory. Both supports and opposition of making it mandatory has their arguments and experiences. Although in both ways there are businesses, contributing in development of better society and making our environment and ecosystem better and sustainable. Although there are greater number of businesses who are doing nothing or very small contribution in this regards.

In current times Corporate Social Responsibility focuses on improving Education. Health, eradicating poverty and helping people in fighting with hunger. This is also contributing in improving democracy and citizenship, fighting with corruption. The CSR has also focus on protecting rights of people, protecting basic human rights, protecting cultural heritage. Protecting environment and ecology is one of the core work of the CSR initiatives by the corporate. Majority of these work through-out the world is voluntary, although some regulations exist in this context. India is the only country till date who made it mandatory for the defined group of corporate.

The Indian context: In India also there are a general understanding of role of businesses for social well-being. Both businesses and society were agreed on this role this role was as JRD Tata says ‘social responsibility of business should be viewed as something over and above their normal functions’. He observed "In a poor country like ours, in which so many of the people are economically deprived and oppressed, the social obligations of business organization as I conceive them must go beyond the accepted routine duties of making a good product, selling it at a fair price, paying their wages, providing good working conditions to labor and paying taxes in full. In every city, town or village, large and small there is always need for improvement, for help, for relief, for leadership and for guidance. I suggest that the most significant contribution organized industry can make is by identifying itself with the life and problems of the people of the community to which it belongs and by applying its resources, skills and talents to the extent that it can reasonably spare them to serve and help them." similarly GD Birla said “Let's pledge to work for building up new industries and enlargement of scope of all, means of production and give an impetus to private and community initiative to make a great and prosperous nation" Tata and Birla groups were investing for the development of the corporate before independence. After the

independence this got moment. Although many industries were run by the government. Since the liberalization many multinational and national companies came in Indian market. Along with business some of them also started some social initiatives. In 2013 by amendment of company laws India become 1st country of the world to make it compulsory for the businesses comes under defined criteria.

India has done amendment in its company act 1948 and make CSR compulsory. The act become Functional since April 2014. The law didn't defined CSR but defined some activity which will come under CSR.

Corporate social responsibility in India is becoming one of major stakeholder of social development after government. Corporate social responsibility is focusing on multiple problems of the society which includes education, health and livelihood. Corporate social responsibility in India is getting more and more prominence. The core challenge of CSR is proper implementation and better professionalism in the sector. The organizations also feel challenges in finding right partner for implementing their projects.

Current Indian CSR Overview: After CSR become compulsory education and health got major amount of resources from CSR. Many corporate groups focuses on improving infrastructure and quality of education and health. Another sector which got attention of CSR initiatives is livelihood related programs. This includes skill base training and placement/these initiatives includes all age groups and all strata of the Indian society. Here is the table related to expenditure of CSR since it become compulsory-

Development Sectors	Amount Spent FY 2014-15 (INR Cr.)	Amount Spent FY 2015-16 (INR Cr.)	Amount Spent FY 2016-17 (INR Cr.)	Amount Spent FY 2017-18 (INR Cr.)

1	Clean Ganga Fund	5.47	32.82	24.37	2.11
2	Education, Differently Abled, Livelihood	3,188.09	4,942.55	5,511.29	3,486.76
3	Encouraging Sports	57.61	138.92	178.52	121.94
4	Environment, Animal Welfare, Conservation Of Resources	853.99	972.34	1,311.15	1,006.36
5	Gender Equality , Women Empowerment , Old Age Homes , Reducing Inequalities	189.92	342.46	463.49	274.79
6	Health, Eradicating Hunger, Poverty And Malnutrition, Safe Drinking Water , Sanitation	2,525.92	4,607.51	3,640.19	1,773.53
7	Heritage Art And Culture	117.37	119.08	304.42	212.42
8	Other Sectors (Technology Incubator And Benefits To Armed Forces And Admin Overheads)	9.50	37.91	60.17	21.44
9	Prime Minister's National Relief Fund	228.18	217.23	157.58	60.40
10	Rural Development	1,059.34	1,379.08	1,548.94	1,066.51
11	Slum Area Development	101.14	14.30	51.46	4.70
12	Swachh Bharat Kosh	113.86	325.19	183.83	118.69
13	Any Other Fund	277.09	332.91	417.98	215.66
14	NEC/ Not Mentioned	1,338.39	1,065.22	388.95	0.00
Grand Total (in Cr.)		10,065.93	14,366.29	13,464.60	8,365.35

Source-national CSR Portal

If we can see this data we can easily identify that there is continuously increase in the CSR expenditure. In the national CSR portal it is mentioned that there are large number of companies (around 70%) which are spending less than prescribed by law. So there will be increase in this and this increase will be significant one. here is some estimate of CSR by CSRBOX and NGOBOX for 2019-2020-

- Overall prescribed CSR for all listed and unlisted companies will be in the range of INR 16500-18000 Cr.
- Top 10 Companies will contribute almost 1/5th of the total CSR Fund.
- 30 companies will spend over INR 100 Cr. each on CSR projects, while 25 companies will spend between INR 50-100 Cr. on CSR projects.
- Almost 115 companies will spend between INR 10-50 Cr. on CSR projects.
- Banking and finance sector companies will contribute almost 1/5th of the total CSR fund.

If we can see the sectors focused in the above table we can easily find that these are the core sectors which are the concerns of the social workers. One of the core challenge of a social worker is mobilizing the resources and needed technologies. These CSR opportunities gives social worker a golden opportunity to use the resources for improving quality of their work and also improve the environment and society qualitatively and significantly. Majority of schools of social work is trying to place their student in CSR related work. Similarly many businesses and corporate groups looking towards these schools for better professionals for these type of work. Now this becomes important to school and department of social work to include CSR in its syllabus. This is also important that this syllabus should not only help student to understand the theoretical aspects of CSR but also they should have well understanding of its business and social implications. They must be well understood about various laws and policies related to CSR. They should also be trained about various compliance related to this. So the study has adopted following criteria to analyze the course and syllabus of the CSR:

- What type of the Course by the Schools/departments e.g. degree (specialization), diploma, certificate, Elective, a chapter, a unit.
- What is the content of the course e.g. Theories, models, social and business implication, laws, policies etc.
- How much time given for the Course.

Data and analysis: Total 25 department and institution was selected for the purpose of these study. These all institution have at-least MSW Course in the program run by them. These department are mixed of both government and private institutions.
Course:

- Only 2 School/department of social work running diploma/certificate course in social work which is only about 8.25% of total sample.
- Around 25% (7/25) of these schools/departments have some type of elective/course on Corporate Social Responsibility as part of MSW syllabus.
- No schools/Departments have full-fledged degree programme or specialization on Corporate Social Responsibility.
- Some of these schools/department have CSR Cell to implement CSR projects but how they are preparing their student for these project of CSR are not found categorically. Example is TISS Mumbai and Loyala College.
- These Courses are run primarily by those schools and department who has HR or Industrial relations in their specializations. Some are running as part of these specializations. This indicates that they have some course in Their MSW but it can be limited to only students of those specialization.
- In MSW and department/schools of social work this contain Concept, theories, Models, approaches, history, policy, rules etc. Basically the focus is on social aspects of corporate. No course is offering its business aspects and how the social worker will be more useful for CSR.
- Majority of the Schools Have one or 2 units on CSR as part of their MSW programs which is around of 6-10 hours. One Departments are running diploma course of one year and one department is running certificate program of 6 month.

For the comparison purpose same university's department/schools of management were selected. Some other prominent institute like IIMs also considered for this study. From business schools/department following information found.

- Majority (all from selected sample) of business school teach CSR in their core courses.
- There are many schools which are running Degree course at post graduate level with specialization on CSR. Many one year diploma courses also run by these institutions.
- In the MBA syllabus majority of the institute have full course on CSR. Although here also specialization like HR has major focus on this. But in MBA courses approximately all courses has CSR as part of study.

- Core part of syllabus of CSR course have understanding of CSR meaning concepts and theories, Policies, laws and its compliance, business implications and business strategies etc.

So it is found that Schools/departments of social work are paying no or very less attention on the education of the CSR. This is quite concerning as CSR become compulsory in India and professionals are needed who have depth of understanding of CSR and its implication of the society. MSW course is well rooted to understand individual and society but the corporate part is missing in this course. Similarly CSR course run by Business schools have good amount of focus on business aspects of CSR but they are missing the social aspects of CSR.

Conclusion and suggestions: Finding suggest that there is lack of courses on CSR in Social work schools/ departments. The course content also need to broaden and this should include the required skill set for these schools.

These findings also draw our attention that only HR specialization of social work is focusing on this but as we can see that CSR expanding is ranging majority of the sectors related to work of social worker. So it is suggested that CSR education should be part of core course of MSW or MA in social work. The researcher also found that social work education in majority of institutions is lacking current requirement of the field of work. It is suggested that through the help of industries, businesses and academicians this should be corrected and improved.

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